

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh Alisher ugli

The 4th year student of the Faculty of pedagogy and psychology,
Fergana State University

Maxamadjonov Jakhongir Zokirjon ugli

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 2nd year student of the faculty

Sobirova Azizaxon Maribjon kizi

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 2nd year student of the faculty

ABSTRACT

Today it is difficult to imagine our life without modern technology. They are also very important in education. This article talks about the use of innovative technologies in the educational activities of educational organizations.

Key words: innovative technologies, cultural values, human potential, personality and abilities, educational content, modern requirements

The 21st century can rightfully be considered a flourishing age of innovative technologies that are actively entering the most diverse areas of human activity, and among them education naturally becomes one of the most important.

Innovative technologies act as one of the foundations of the activity of social processes, as well as a condition for their interdependence. The information space expands human potential through the global network, allows overcoming geographical and political boundaries, makes the world's cultural values accessible to everyone for reflection, and encourages the imagination of the sphere of human life. In this regard, at present, the pedagogical teams of the preschool educational organization are actively introducing innovative technologies to their work. Therefore, the main task of preschool educators is to choose the methods and forms of organizing work with children, innovative pedagogical technologies that optimally match the set goal of personality development. [1, 248]

Undoubtedly, innovative processes at the current stage of society's development affect the preschool education system, first of all, as the first stage of revealing the

child's potential abilities. Development of preschool education, transition to a new level of quality cannot be done without the development of innovative technologies.

Therefore, innovations define new methods, forms, tools, technologies used in pedagogical practice, aimed at the development of the child's personality and abilities. However, modern pedagogical technologies of preschool education are aimed at the implementation of state standards of preschool education. Therefore, the main task of preschool teachers is to choose the methods and forms of organizing work with children, innovative pedagogical technologies that optimally correspond to the set goal of personality development. [4, 59]

Nowadays, due to the wide range of opportunities to achieve efficiency in the educational process based on innovative technologies in an unconventional way, interests and aspirations for it are growing. The center of the process of innovative technologies (non-traditional method) is the child. The wide use of interactive methods has a good effect on the effective implementation of the process of raising a child as a well-rounded person. Because, in this process, the educator acts as a guide, consultant, organizer, manager of the child's activities, and forms more independence, creativity and willful qualities in children. [6, 89]

An important condition of the interactive educational environment is that it prioritizes joint, cooperative activity between the learner (child) and the teacher (educator). It is based on the cooperation and mutual understanding and activity of the participants of the pedagogical process.

As a result of these interactions, the child:

- in the educational process, they are forced not to be indifferent, to be responsible, to think and act independently, to create and to search;
- interested in mastering educational content;
- have effective communication skills;
- learns to effectively plan and organize his activities;
- adapts to understand and react to the actions and appeals of others;
- learns to defend his opinion in front of his teammates and listen to others.

Choosing a modern method, the educator should prepare the necessary tools in advance. At present, practitioners have such an opinion that "when working in interactive methods, the pedagogue moves less, children work more and find the solution to the problem themselves." This view is essentially a shallow conclusion. Because whether it is a simple method or an interactive method, the pedagogue is the owner of the process. The quality of the work he did before training, the right choice of tools are of great importance. If the method that requires a lot of tools is used, then the pedagogue is considered to have performed the appropriate action before the training. If the pedagogue makes a lot of effort in the process, it means that the chosen

method requires it, or he did not prepare the necessary equipment in time. Interactive methods encourage the pedagogue to be more creative and responsible than ever before. That is, all participants must be active in the process. [5, 74]

There are various interactive methods for teaching preschool children. Including:

Children sit in a circle and perform various exercises. The advantage of this method, compared to the method of passing children in rows, is that no child feels that he is separated, that is, someone is behind and someone is ahead. Not every child is left out of the educator's eyes and attention. Everyone feels "equal".

In this method, several children perform different tasks in a circle. These children in the middle are like fish in an aquarium. Their every move is closely watched by the children sitting around the circle.

"Muzyoralar" is otherwise known as dating. In short, this activity helps children behave, get to know each other and create an atmosphere of mutual trust in the group. Invites them to participate and support each other.

In the "Names" game, the first child says his name. And then he mentions one of his qualities that starts with whatever letter his name starts with. (for example, Shaira-sho'kh). At the same time, it can be reflected with actions that express this character.

In the "History of the name" children take turns to tell why this name is given and by whom.

In Ten Years After Me, each child says their name and talks about their life ten years from now.

"Favorite Animals" tells what animal every child would like to become if they could. The name of the animal is indicated by its characteristic actions.

The group of children "I want to introduce you" is divided into pairs, and after that each child introduces his partner to the group members. [3, 159]

In conclusion, it can be said that a demanding pedagogue, who loves his profession and approaches it responsibly, is an example of activity in the process, his creativity encourages children to think. Interactive methods are a factor that ensures that children are educated at the level of modern requirements. The most important factor that determines the quality of education is children's interest in education. Children take an active part in the process they are interested in and become creative.

REFERENCES:

- 1.Korobkov A.V., Golovin V.A., Maslyakov V.A. Physical education. M.: Higher. school, 1983;
- 2.Kots Ya.M., Sports Physiology. M.: Physical culture and sport, 1986;
- 3.Adams V. S., Zimmer B. E. Understanding Psychology. –New York: McGraw-Hill Inc., 1990. –296 p;

4. Anderson Th., Forrester K. Reading then Writing: From Source to Essay. – New York: McGraw-Hill Inc., 1992. –523 p;

5. Arends R. Learning to Teach. –New York: McGraw-Hill Inc., 1994. –549 p;

6. Bellack A. A. The Language of the Classroom. –New York: Teachers College Press, 1996. –274 p;

7. Brumft C. Communicative Methodology in Language Teaching. – Cambridge University Press, 1992. –166 p;

8. Byrne D. Classroom Observation Tasks. - Cambridge University Press, 1992. – 120 p;

9. Alisher o'g'li, E.O. and Zokirjon o'g'li, M.J., 2022. The Role of Psychology in the Treatment of Heart Failure in Humans. European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science, 5, pp.500-502.

10. Ахмедов, Акмал Юсуфович. "БЎЛАЖАК ПСИХОЛОГЛАРДА КОММУНИКАТИВ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК-ПСИХОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ." *Gospodarka I Innowacje*. 22 (2022): 220-222.